

Taking action to prevent and mitigate pollution of groundwater bodies

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Case studies specifications, requirements, and Knowledge base

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3	BEN	IMT	INSTITUT MINES-TELECOM	FR
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Executive summary

In NINFA WP1 (Case studies specifications, requirements and knowledge gathering), a general framework and basis for the work in NINFA will be set up. In this sense, information regarding case studies specifications, data collection and compilation in the knowledge base, common KPIs monitoring methodology and water treatment technologies will be gathered. In addition, within WP1, a continuous investigation of the evolution of the regulation will be performed to ensure adequation and compliance of NINFA approach to National and European legislations.

The NINFA Deliverable D1.1 is the output of task T1.1 and contains preliminary results from task T1.2. It presents the description of the case studies, and initial version of the SOTA in sensors and water treatment technologies for GW, and a summary of related regulations. As D1.1 is the public version of a more complete deliverable (D1.3), validation metrics and project Expected Outcomes (EO) are not detailed. It will serve as input for Tasks T1.2, T1.3, and T1.4. The deliverable is structured as follows:

- General introduction describing GW pollution sources and NINFA strategy
- Case Studies Description
- State of The Art in sensors and water treatment technologies
- Overall conclusions

List of Abbreviations

AC	Activated Carbon
ADMV	Aquífer Detrític del Miocè del Vallès
AOP	Advanced Oxidation Process
ARB	Antibiotic Resistant Bacteria
ARG	Antibiotic Resistance Genes
AVAT	Aquífer del Ventall alluvial de Terrassa
BF	Biofiltration
CEC	Contaminants of Emerging Concern
CS	Case Study
DSS	Decision Support System
DTS	Distributed Temperature Sensing
EU	European Union
FBG	Fibre Bragg Gratings
GW	Groundwater
HC	Hydrocarbons
HM	Heavy Metals
HTC	Hydrothermal Carbonization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MP	Microplastics
NBS	Nature Based Solutions

SOTA	State of the art
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Waste Water Treatment Plant

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1 Introduction

Groundwater (GW) is a key resource for water supply for people and nature, which must stay resilient and healthy, also under global and climate changes. Around 35% of the area of GW bodies are affected by diffuse pollution with pesticides and nutrients derived from agriculture and farming, which leads to eutrophication. Other pollution sources, including sewage from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and runoff infiltration in cities (especially during storm events), jeopardize GW quality with contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), such as pharmaceuticals, and antibiotic resistance genes (ARG), hydrocarbons (HC), heavy metals (HM), and microplastics (MP), among others. Since water bodies are interconnected, contaminants end up in rivers, wetlands, lakes, and oceans. Moreover, aquifer exploitation for water consumption leads to increased pressure on GW resources, which also affects their quality, especially in coastal aquifers, due to saline intrusion. These problems may be aggravated by global (industrialization, high rate of urbanization, and population growth) and climate change effects (longer drought periods leading to a lack of aquifers natural recharge, or an increased sea level worsening saline intrusion).

NINFA seeks to develop and validate a novel holistic strategy for efficient groundwater management and protection based on an early-warning Decision Support System (DSS) and knowledge base (the NINFA Platform) fed by a series of innovative and cost-effective monitoring, modelling and treatment solutions (NINFA Solutions) considering diverse pollutants and synergistic effects regarding stressors derived from climate and global changes, with the aim of preventing GW contamination, protecting its quality and enhancing its resilience. The NINFA platform and solutions will be tested in 8 case studies which are in the European Union (EU) and International Case Studies (CS).

The NINFA Solutions that will be developed include innovative monitoring strategies and novel sensors (monitoring groundwater properties and quality), water treatment technologies (prevention of groundwater pollution and generation of fit-for-purpose reclaimed water) and GW flow and reactive-transport models (prediction of groundwater pollution). The sensors and technologies will be developed and optimised at lab scale and further validated in selected case studies at pilot scale.

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a description of the case studies where NINFA solutions will be implemented to define baseline conditions and highlight the groundwater quality concern as well as to describe the technologies that will be implemented and to present the proposed Key Performance indicators (KPIs) and validation strategy.

2 Description of case studies

The 8 EU and International case studies were chosen to represent diverse environments, socio-economic contexts and pollution and climate/global change challenges. This will allow a robust validation of the project solutions, activities, and interventions. Out of the 8 case studies, the 4 European case studies have been chosen as demo sites for the implementation and validation of proposed NINFA solutions whereas international case studies aimed to increase NINFA platform database. This section presents a description of the 4 European case studies.

2.1 CS1: Achterhoek, Gelderland, Netherlands

2.1.1 Location

The Achterhoek is a region located in the eastern part of the Netherlands, specifically in the province of Gelderland. It is situated between the IJssel River to the west, the German border to the east, and the Twente region to the north. The Achterhoek consists of various municipalities, including Winterswijk, Doetinchem, Berkelland, and Oost Gelre (**Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.**). This rural area is not densely populated and features large amounts of pastureland and natural landscapes from Roman times. The region has large forests in Montferland and sand flats near Doetinchem.

Figure 1: The Achterhoek region's location in Netherlands, as well as the region's boundaries and cities

2.1.2 Climate

The Achterhoek area has an oceanic climate with rainfall throughout the year. The average annual temperature is 14°C. The warmest time of the year is generally early July, with highs around 24.1°C and temperatures rarely dropping below 12.8°C at night. The area generally receives 95.28 mm of precipitation monthly and has 184.17 rainy days¹. Droughts have been increasingly common in the Netherlands in recent years, and it is projected that they will become more severe and frequent in the future because of climate change².

2.1.3 Socio-economic description

The Achterhoek region of the Netherlands has a socio-economic situation characterized by a diverse range of industries, demographics, and challenges. Here are some key aspects of Achterhoek's socio-economic profile:

- **Diversified Economy:** agriculture and manufacturing are two of the region's most important economic sectors. However, there has been a shift towards a more diversified economy, including manufacturing, services, and tourism. The region is known for its metalworking, engineering, food processing, and high-tech industries³.
- **SMEs and Entrepreneurship:** Achterhoek has a strong presence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and a culture of entrepreneurship. These businesses play a vital role in the local economy, driving innovation, creating employment opportunities, and contributing to the overall economic growth of the region.
- **Employment Challenges:** Like many rural areas, Achterhoek faces challenges related to employment. While the region has several job opportunities, there can be a shortage of specific skills, leading to difficulties in attracting and retaining talent. Efforts are being made to bridge the skills gap through collaborations between businesses, educational institutions, and government initiatives.
- **Demographics:** Achterhoek has a relatively dispersed population across its rural municipalities, with a combination of larger towns and smaller villages. The region has seen a trend of outmigration of younger residents seeking employment and educational opportunities in urban areas. However, Achterhoek also attracts retirees and individuals seeking a quieter rural lifestyle.
- **Tourism and Recreation:** Achterhoek is known for its scenic landscapes, historic heritage, and outdoor recreational opportunities. Tourism has become an important sector, attracting visitors who enjoy activities such as cycling, hiking, and exploring the region's castles, museums, and cultural events. The tourism industry contributes to the local economy through accommodations, restaurants, and other related services.
- **Connectivity and Infrastructure:** Achterhoek has been investing in infrastructure development to improve connectivity within the region and to other parts of the country. This includes road networks, public transportation, and digital connectivity, which are essential for attracting businesses, residents, and tourists.
- **Collaborative Initiatives:** Achterhoek region has a strong sense of community, and collaborative initiatives between local governments, businesses, educational institutions, and residents are prevalent. These collaborations aim to foster innovation, economic growth, cultural activities, and social cohesion within the region.

The average annual income per capita in the Achterhoek area is 35,500 Euros.

2.1.4 Hydrogeology

In the Achterhoek area there are four sub-basins, three of them originated in Germany (Schipbeek, Berkel, and Oude IJssel) (**Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.**). The Baakse Beek is the only sub-basin that is located entirely within the borders of the Achterhoek. The water system of Achterhoek is therefore partly dependent on the water management of German neighbours and international agreements. The NINFA Project will focus on developing a framework to improve the performance of the groundwater system in the Baakse Beek area.

Baakse Beek catchment is centrally located in the Triangle of Zutphen, Ruurlo, and Hengelo. The current landscape is predominantly agricultural. In addition, large parts of the estate zone are part of or designated as Gelders Nature Network (GNN). Within this, the stream valley forms an important ecological corridor from the East Netherlands' plateau to the flood plains of the IJssel.

Figure 2: Achterhoek area sub-basins

The Rhine IJssel Water Board has been working on the development of this area to create a robust and future-proof water system in the Baakse Beek estate zone. Although this area is part of the GNN and its nature is protected, it has been drying up, which means that the current groundwater situation is not optimal due to human influence. Measures are being sought to create a climate-proof, robust water system in which the various functions, including agriculture, are strengthened and a better situation is created for the landscape and heritage.

The Achterhoek region's overall hydrogeological characteristics include a conductive surface and a highly conductive subsurface, as well as the presence of clay lenses that act as aquitards. Because the water that infiltrates and recharges groundwater flows quickly through the soil, uplands in general are particularly vulnerable to seasonal precipitation changes. Anthropogenic drainage activities in rural and urban settings further reduced subsurface residence periods. Groundwater levels in these areas' sources are dynamic on average because they are heavily dependent on precipitation fluctuations; however, at the regional scale, less dynamism can be recognized (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Hydrological characteristics of the Achterhoek aquifer at two locations: (a) co-ordinates: 208630, 459520 (RD), (b): co-ordinates: 250225, 447732 (RD). Data obtained from <https://www.dinoloket.nl/>

The subsurface area includes three aquifer layers and an aquitard between levels two and three. The hydrological basis was a thick clay layer from the Breda formation. The first layer was built on a Bortel formation sandy unit, the second on a Kreftenheye formation sandy unit, and the third on an Oosterhout formation sandy unit. The aquitard is related to an Oosterhout formation clayey unit. Layers 1 and 2 can be considered as a single unconfined aquifer, while layer 3 can be regarded as a confined aquifer⁴. The hydraulic conductivities of the three layers are approximately ranged between 5-10, 20-50, and 1-2.5 m/d for the horizontal conductivities of layers 1, 2, and 3, and 0.0035 m/d for the vertical conductivity of the semi-confining bed beneath layer 2, based on TNO REGIS data⁵.

Groundwater is supplied at Vitens pumping station 't Klooster for approximately 299,882 residents. Vitens manages the 't Klooster water extraction area as a nature reserve⁶. It is allowed to pump up 5.0 million cubic meters of water from the soil there yearly. The extracted groundwater is subjected to in-situ treatment processes before pumping into the drinking water network to remove iron materials⁶. Another production site (Vorden) is located southeast of the municipality of Zutphen. Vitens is allowed to extract 3 million cubic meters of water from the soil. Water is pumped up from depths ranging from

20 to 38 meters and then transported to a drinking water production company, where sand filters are used to remove contaminants such as iron and manganese⁷.

2.1.5 Concerns with regards to GW quality

Droughts have been increasingly common in the Netherlands in recent years, and it is projected that they will become more severe and frequent in the future as a result of climate change². By comparing the situation of the water balance (year-round) in 1950 with that of 2020, it can be seen how the water system of Achterhoek has changed quantitatively from the past to now. In general, amounts of input (i.e. precipitation, inflow water from Germany & effluent) and output (evaporation, discharge to IJssel river and groundwater extraction) in the water balance has increased, but the proportions remain largely the same. The groundwater level was depleted, although precipitation (main recharge parameter) has increased.

The summer of 2018 was an extreme example of drought in the Netherlands, with high temperatures and below-average precipitation causing a significant precipitation deficit. Using 2018 as an example, the following conclusions can be drawn: in extremely dry summers, there is little precipitation and little supply from Germany. However, the output of the water balance during these summers is extremely high, creating a huge water demand that cannot be compensated by the (deeper) groundwater reserves, resulting in severe drought damage.

The area is vulnerable due to the relatively poor water retention in the sandy underground, which in periods of drought leads to higher concentrations of pollutants. As mentioned, agriculture is one of the major economic activities and thus in the last years, elevated concentrations of nitrate and pesticides were detected in the pumped water.

Therefore, it is necessary to study the impact of the drought on the quality and quantity of the available groundwater in the Achterhoek area. As a result, the Dutch government was obligated to take steps to mitigate the drought's effects on the area's groundwater system. Several projects were implemented to mitigate the effects of the drought, with a focus on storing surplus water from heavy precipitation in winter to be used during drought periods. However, it is unclear how much of an impact these measures could (had) on groundwater quality.

2.1.6 Actions within NINFA

Within the NINFA project, the effect of drought and drought-relief measures on groundwater quality will be investigated and modelled in the Baakse Beek area with a focus on nitrates and micropollutants. This will be done through two steps tackled in Work Package (WP) 2:

1. Develop a cost-efficient monitoring strategy based on the integration of existing sensors and analytical approaches with innovative tools.
2. Assess the existing sources and pathways of GW pollution, their synergistic effects with stressors such as droughts and floods or prevention/mitigation measures, by testing and validating hydrogeological and reactive transport models for nutrients, pesticides, and emerging contaminants from wastewater. Furthermore, it is proposed to create management

scenarios and propose measures to mitigate the effects of drought on the groundwater system.

2.2 CS2: Los Alcázares, Murcia, Spain

2.2.1 Location

Los Alcázares is a Spanish municipality in the autonomous community of Murcia, in the south-east of Spain (Figure 4). Los Alcázares is located on the coast of Mar Menor, which is the Europe's largest saltwater lagoon with almost 170 km², and it is an area of great ecological, geological and scenic importance. Its surrounding areas are particularly rich in landscape values, and it is an area where up to ten approved environmental protection figures converge. It is also a protected area in the Natura 2000 Network, classified as a Special Area of Conservation and Special Protection Area for Birds (SPA) as "Open Spaces and Islands of the Mar Menor". In 1994 it was included on the Ramsar Convention list for the conservation and sustainable utilisation of wetlands.

Figure 4: Location of Los Alcázares, Murcia.

2.2.2 Climate information

The region enjoys a semi-arid Mediterranean climate, with mild winters (an average of 11°C in December and January) and warm summers (with maximum temperatures over 30 °C). The average annual temperature is 18 °C. There is around 319 mm rainfall per year, concentrated in the months of September to January leading to annual episodes of droughts and floods⁸.

2.2.3 Socio-Economic description

Los Alcázares has a permanent population of 17,603 which rises to over 100,000 during the summer holiday season, as tourism is one of the main activities of the region.

Agriculture is the main land use, both rainfed (including almond, winter cereals and olive, covering 6% of the area) and intensively irrigated (including horticultural crops and citrus trees, 31% of the area). Drip irrigation is the most extended practice (90 %) due to water scarcity. Until the early 1970s, the agrarian system was mainly drylands, with scattered irrigated agriculture fed by wells, powered first by windmills and later by electric pumps. Then in the 1979 it was supported with the arrival of water from the Tagus-Segura water transfer channel. The Tagus-Segura water transfer channel allocates up to 12,000 m³/y for irrigation in the Campo de Cartagena. For comparison, water as natural precipitation over the entire watershed amounts to $\approx 40,000$ m³/y.

In the last 40 years, agricultural land under irrigation has grown by ten-fold, currently covering about 30–38% of the basin of the Murcia Region ($\approx 40,000$ – $50,000$ ha)⁹. As can be seen in Table 1, in the 21st century, the increase in the irrigated area has slowed down and, in the last decade, it has even stabilized¹⁰.

Description	1980	1991	1998	2004	2010	2015
Irrigated Area (ha)	14,521	23,911	34,328	39,328	42,253	43,071
Irrigated Demand (Mm³/yr)	94.39	155.42	223.14	223.14	270.50	258.40
Irrigated Rate (m³/ha/yr)	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6000

Table 1: Temporal evolution of the irrigated area in Campo de Cartagena in terms of average irrigation endowments¹⁰

The average income per capita in Los Alcázares was 21,236 Euros in 2021, significantly lower than the national average of 27,870 Euros. Unemployment is one of the most important issues in the region with an average unemployment rate of 11.34 % in 2022, slightly lower than the national average of 13.0 %.

2.2.4 Hydrogeology

The catchment of the Mar Menor coastal lagoon is the Campo de Cartagena plain, with a surface area of 1316 km². The plain has a gentle slope towards the east (1%) and is surrounded by low mountain ranges except in the east, where the lagoon is located¹⁰. The Campo de Cartagena area is associated to three groundwater bodies: the Carrascoy Triassic aquifer, the Victorias Triassic aquifer and the aquifer also called Campo de Cartagena (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Location of the aquifers of the Campo de Cartagena region

The neogenic coastal soil that forms this zone has a roughly 1000 m-thick Neogene-Quaternary filling from the Tertiary period on a bedrock of Triassic marble and constitutes a post-orogenic depression of the Baetic Cordillera geological region. This region has a predominance of marl, alternating with sandstone and the conglomerates that form the Tortonian aquifer stratum; in the Messinian stratum, sandstone and bioclastic calcarenite alternate, giving shape to the upper Miocene. In the other stratum, the Pliocene aquifer layer is formed from sandstone and white marl. Within the Tertiary stretches is the Quaternary stratum, which consists of sand, silt, clay, conglomerates, caliche and sandstone (Figure 6). The various aquifers are geologically well-defined and are separated by thick aquitard layers. Within this multi-layered coastal aquifer, the Pliocene and Messinian stretches have special hydrogeological relevance due to their intensive exploitation¹⁰.

Figure 6: Geological map and cross section of the Campo Cartagena area¹⁰

The area is stratified into permeable layers, which sometimes causes problems for the hydraulic continuity of the groundwater body. The tectonics of this zone, with its barriers and divisions, also affects the hydraulic continuity, giving rise to local hydrogeological independencies that cause general heterogeneity and that generate variability in the data obtained from nearby areas. In turn, more than 1200 private wells are officially registered, and many of them exploit several aquifers through internal communication, which allows for artificial connections between stretches of water¹⁰.

Natural recharge to the multi-layer aquifer system is small and depends on the respective outcrop areas of each aquifer. The Quaternary aquifer is also recharged by the irrigation return flow, complex combination of multiple sources of surface and groundwaters. Farmers mix the different sources of water and store them in open air water reservoirs before their application to crops. The mixing proportions between groundwater and Tagus-Segura water transfer channel water mainly depend on the availability of Tagus-Segura water transfer channel water¹¹.

Around 2000 boreholes are officially numbered. Many of them are screened in several aquifers, allowing an artificial connection between the different water masses, and possibly complicating the recharge patterns. In most cases, the technical description of the borehole is not available, and the precise depths of screens are unknown¹¹.

2.2.5 Concerns with regards to GW quality

The Campo de Cartagena groundwater mass was declared at risk of not reaching good quantitative or chemical status by the Segura Hydrographic Confederation in July, 2020. As mentioned earlier, the area experiences intense agricultural activity. It is an important supply point to European markets, especially for vegetables during winter. Water demand for irrigation is met by the Tagus-Segura Water Transfer (1/3 of demand) and groundwater (2/3 of the demand)¹². This has led to an overexploitation of the lower layers of the multi-layer aquifer. While the lower layers of the aquifer do have a problem of overexploitation, the upper aquifer, formed in the Quaternary period, which discharges into the Mar Menor, does not have a problem of water quantity, rather the opposite. Seawater intrusion, the filtration of irrigation water, which has increased since the construction of the transfer, as well as periodic intense rains, have made the water table so high that water surfaces on to the ground at some points¹³.

The extremely high intensity of agricultural production is sustained by fertigation although high amounts of manure are also applied, particularly in order to condition the soils of vegetable-oriented farms prior to planting⁹. This has led to pollution of the upper layers of the aquifer with nitrates, pesticides and nutrients. Data from control points during the period of 2015 to 2019 (Table 2) show that average nitrate concentrations of 20 out of the 24 points exceeded the 50 mg/L limit stated in the Groundwater Directive (Directive 2006/118/EC)¹⁴.

Control Point	Average NO ₃ (mg/L)	Aquifer	Mass name
ca0731020	40.0	100-a	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731020s	96.0	100-p-q	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca07000022	211.0	100-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca07000030s	161.0	100-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731002	84.2	100-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731021	57.0	100-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
Ca0731-alb3	83.7	100-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
Ca07ni-42	49.3	100-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca07ni-52s	162.0	100-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731003	165.3	100-q	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731006	215.0	100-q	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731-alb1	200.0	100-q	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731-alb4	81.0	100-q	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731-sic03	387.0	100-q	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca07ni-44	250.0	100-q	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca07ni-49	244.0	100-q	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731026	41.0	100-q-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731-alb2	88.4	100-q-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731-edsal	110.8	100-q-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731-pobres	62.5	100-q-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731-sic02	157.0	100-q-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca0731-sic02s	215.0	100-q-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
ca07ni-37	96.4	100-q-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA

ca07ni-40s	40.0	100-q-p	CAMPO DE CARTAGENA
*100-a-p-q. Campo de Cartagena Aquifer (possible interconnected Andalucian, Pilocene and Quaternary sections); 100-p. Campo de Cartagena Aquifer (Pilocene); 100-q. Campo de Cartagena Aquifer (Quaternary); 100-p-q. Campo de Cartagena Aquifer (possible interconnected Pilocene and Quaternary sections)			

Table 2: Average nitrates concentrations from 2015-2019 at control points

Due to its connection with the Campo de Cartagena watershed, the Mar Menor receives nutrients and in the recent years, suffers a severe eutrophication crisis resulting in reduction in water transparency and several episodes of anoxia (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Anoxia episodes in Mar Menor: "green soup" and fish mortality.

2.2.6 Actions within NINFA

Several solutions will be tested in this case study under WP2 and WP3:

- Robust, real time and affordable sensors will be developed in the lab will be tested at certain sites for GW monitoring and early-detection of pollutants.
- Assess the existing sources and pathways of GW pollution, their synergistic effects with stressors such as droughts and floods or prevention/mitigation measures, by testing and validating hydrogeological and reactive transport models for pollutants of interest.
- Develop a train of treatment including membrane-based technologies, Advanced Oxidation Processes and nature-based solutions, to minimize nutrients, pesticides and other pollutants (metals and antibiotics from manure) leaching to GWs.

2.3 CS3: Terrassa, Barcelona, Spain

2.3.1 Location

Terrassa is a city located in the comarca del Vallès Occidental (Figure 8) with an extension of about 70.2 km², which belongs to the province of Barcelona, one of the four provinces that are part of

Catalonia, Spain. Terrassa was founded as the Roman city of Egara in the 1st century, close to the Vallparadís torrent, which originates in Matadepera and passes through Terrassa.

Figure 8: Location of Terrassa in Spain

The municipality of Terrassa is located at the foot of the pre-coastal mountain range. To the north of the municipality there is the pre-littoral overhang, which separates the Ebro foreland basin located to the north of the overhang from the intramontane basins, located to the south of the overhang. The intramontane basins have Neogene and Quaternary ages (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Geological map of the area of Terrassa.

Source: Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia (2021) (text in Catalan).

2.3.2 Climate information

Terrassa is characterised by a Mediterranean climate. In the last 10-20 years, the winter temperatures range between 5°C to 12°C in December and January and can get to a maximum of about 30°C during the summer months.

In Terrassa, there are two seasons where precipitation is more abundant, in spring and autumn (Figure 10). Autumn is the time when precipitation is usually more abundant, especially in October, while in spring it is the month of April. The difference between the two seasons is that though there is more rainfall in autumn, it lasts less thus creating a season of torrential rains.

Figure 10 : Average precipitation and rainfall days (2012-2022)¹⁵

The average annual precipitation in Catalonia is about 600 mm/year (Servei Meteorològic de Catalunya). In the last 10 years only four years has the precipitation value been higher than this value, while in the other years it has either been lower or has values close to half of this value. The resulting average annual precipitation is 553 mm/year, a value lower than the 600 average precipitation that should have, therefore, there has been a water deficit in the water system, which conditions the recharge of aquifers of the in Terrassa.

2.3.3 Socio-Economic description

Terrassa has a population of approximately 220,000 where the most predominant sector is trade, although industry, construction and agriculture are also important sectors.

2.3.4 Hydrogeology

Terrassa is located on two aquifers; the more superficial aquifer called the Aquifer del Ventall alluvial de Terrassa (AVAT) and the deeper called the Aquifer Detrític del Miocè del Vallès (ADMV).

2.3.4.1 Aquifer del Ventall alluvial de Terrassa (AVAT)

The AVAT is an aquifer formed by an intercalation of gravels, silty and clay matrix sands where major changes in the vertical lithology are contemplated (Figure 11). Calcareous sediments are also observed

although their origin is mainly fluvial and alluvial. Its depth is between 10 and 30 meters and is divided into three units.

Figure 11: Stratigraphic column of AVAT aquifer materials¹⁶

The upper unit, Qv₃, consists of gravel layers with a silty and sandy matrix and a variable degree of cementation. It is supported by abundant calcium carbonate material. Its origin corresponds mainly to sediments from Matadepera and Castellar del Vallès. This unit also corresponds to the base of the Ripoll alluvial aquifer. The unit Qv₄ which corresponds to the central layer and is poorly separated gravel layers with a silty or sandy matrix and has some lenticular levels of silts and clays. The source of these sediments is the same as unit Qv₃. The lower unit Qv_g, is formed by a layer of clay matrix gravels with a variable thickness. It is formed by materials with a high permeability (greater than 10⁻⁶ cm/s) such as gravel and unconsolidated sands.

This aquifer has a transmissivity that is between 300 and 1000 m²/day, the hydraulic conductivity [k] is between 50 - 150 m/day and has an effective porosity between 10 - 15%. The effective porosity is described as the proportion of porosity in a rock or sediment that allows water to pass through it.

The Terrassa aquifer occupies a large part of the municipality of Terrassa (Figure 12), it extends to the north and also occupies the municipality of Matadepera and part of the southeast reaching Sabadell.

Figure 12: Representation of the mass of water that would correspond to the AVAT

2.3.4.2 Aquifer Detrític del Miocè del Vallès (ADMV)

The lower aquifer, the Aquifer Detrític del Miocè del Vallès (ADMV) is a confined aquifer that has low permeability. The fact that it is a confined aquifer means that it is closed by impermeable layers that do not allow water to escape and only receives water through the area where the permeable materials are theoretically located. In this case, the ADMV is not a homogeneous aquifer throughout the area. There is however some evidence found from a hydrochemical study that was carried out and with the various pumping tests along the area, which showed that in some sections it can be considered as a semi-confined aquifer, which would explain the relationship between the two aquifers.

The ADMV aquifer has electrical conductivity values above 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in almost the entire area and the pH values between 7.5 and 8. Some of the parameters such as nitrates, sodium or chloride in some points present anomalous concentrations due to activities related to the salt treatment industry and low-production agro-livestock, which can be harmful for human consumption.

This aquifer is divided into two sub-levels, the ADMVa (upper level) which has a granular composition and the ADMVb (lower level) which is cohesive (Figure 13). The upper level has less potential than the lower level, which is divided into three units:

- The upper unit, Nmbt, corresponds to a formation of breccias and red shales
- The central unit, NMI_m, consists of red and ocher feldspathic quartz shales and sandstones, which include some levels of breccias.
- The NMcc unit which consists of conglomerates with some levels of sandstones with arkose and shale properties.

The transmissivity is between 1 - 30 m²/day and has an effective porosity of 1%.

Figure 13: The aquifers in Terrassa ¹⁶

2.3.5 Concerns with regards to GW quality

Terrassa is located in an area with permeable and porous materials that would allow the passage of rainwater and form the Terrassa aquifer. To calculate vulnerability, the DRASTIC method is used¹⁷. It evaluates the entry of a given pollutant into the saturated zone by weighting 7 variables. As can be seen in the vulnerability map (Figure 14), there are three different areas within the Terrassa area:

1. The first zone, the central area, is an urban area and is all paved. It poses a low risk of pollutants reaching the water-saturated (aquifer) zone and thus has a low vulnerability level.
2. The second zone, areas surrounding surface water, such as the rivers and streams that pass through Terrassa are extremely vulnerable. As they have direct contact with the aquifer, any pollutants entering these areas would directly affect the aquifer.
3. The last zone, the outskirts of the Terrassa are characterized by agricultural farmlands, coniferous forests and other vegetation areas and are marked as moderately vulnerable. Although pollutants could potentially reach the saturated zone, the presence of vegetation poses a natural barrier and makes their infiltration more challenging.

Figure 14 :Terrassa vulnerability map (Source: Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia and Catalan Water Agency (2018)) (text in Catalan).

Currently, the aquifer recharge is mainly performed with rainwater and irrigation excess, to address the risk of saline intrusion due to the proximity to the sea. In the last 10 years, the amount of average annual precipitation has decreased and has therefore affected the recharge of the aquifer. Additionally, the fact that the entire city of Terrassa has been paved/asphalted further negatively impacted aquifer recharge.

No water wells to monitor water quality, neither in terms of conventional contaminants (HCs, HMs,...) nor in terms of contaminants of emerging concern for human and environment health (CECs, ARGs, ARBs, MPs), are available on the territory. However, GW is suspected to be contaminated with urban runoff (HM, HC, MP) since 43.2% of the aquifer area is urban/industrial soil.

2.3.6 Actions within NINFA

NINFA (WP3) will address GW contamination by urban runoff in a selected Terrassa pilot site by testing optimized train of technologies to produce reclaimed water from urban runoff. The use of the reclaimed water for different purposes such as irrigation, street cleaning and/or indirect aquifer recharge will be evaluated. The train of technologies will be based on biological (such as Nature-based solutions, NBS), chemical (advanced oxidation processes, AOPs), and physical processes (membranes). This will enable the removal of HCs and MPs as well as the recovery of selected metals coming from car catalyst and brakes (Platinum (Pt) and Palladium (Pd)).

2.4 CS4 : Butry-sur-Oise, Ile-de-France, France

2.4.1 General description of WWTP at Butry-sur-Oise

Butry -sur-Oise is a community located in the Val-d'Oise department in the Île-de-France region. It is characterized by an Oceanic climate. The winter temperatures range between 5°C to 12°C in December and January and can get to a maximum of about 25°C during the summer months. The yearly average rainfall is measured at about 758 mm.

WWTP at Butry-sur-Oise (Figure 15) treats on average 1163m³/day of wastewater which corresponds to a nominal capacity of 6700 population equivalent (PE). The WWTP has a secondary treatment stage where primary effluent is treated using an extended aeration activated sludge system. It generates about 83 Tons/year (dry solids) of sludge which is initially treated by gravity thickening and then sent to composting sites for further treatment and valorisation. The treated water is then released into the Oise River which is in the Seine-Normandy watershed.

Figure 15 : Aerial view of WWTP at Butry-sur-Oise¹⁸

2.4.2 Concerns with regards to GW quality

The WWTP is located within the Albien-Néocomien aquifer, which has been identified as a strategic resource for emergency drinking water supply due to its proximity to Paris. The Albien sandy-clay aquifer is a deep reservoir located beneath the chalk of the Paris Basin, covering an area of over 100,000 km². It does not outcrop in the Ile-de-France region, but on the edges in Burgundy and

Champagne in particular. Beneath the Albien aquifer, and separated from it by the Aptian clays, lies a calcareous-sandy aquifer of Neocomian age.

The WWTP does not have a specific tertiary treatment for the elimination of CECs, MPs and ARGs, which can lead to their presence in the effluent, along with certain nutrients like nitrates and phosphates. Due to the possible connection of the watershed to aquifer, the GW might present contamination with these pollutants.

2.4.3 Actions within NINFA

Under WP3, NINFA will investigate the tertiary treatment of secondary treated domestic wastewater for possible reuse (focusing on managed aquifer recharge). This will be done by evaluating a combination of low cost AOP, activated carbon (AC) and biofiltration (BF) for the removal of CECs and MPs as well as evaluating the fate of ARGs.

2.5 Summary of case studies

Table 3 summarizes the description of the case studies (CS1 to CS4) and the actions (NINFA solutions) that will be implemented within NINFA.

	CS 1	CS2	CS3	CS4
Climate	Oceanic	Mediterranean	Mediterranean	Oceanic
Rainfall	95.28 mm /month	319 mm/year	553mm/year	758 mm/year
Population	299,882	17,603	220,000	4500 approx.
Hydrogeology	3 sandy layer aquifers and a clayey layer aquitard	3 multilayer (sand, silt, clay ...) aquifers	2 multilayer (sand, clay, silt, quartz, sandstones..) aquifers	2 multi layer (sandy-clay, calcareous-sandy) aquifers
Problem related to GW	Pollution by nitrates and pesticides exacerbated by droughts	Pollution by nitrates and pesticides	Contamination with urban runoff which contains HMs, HCs and MPs	Contamination with WWTP effluent which contains CECs, MPs and ARGs
NINFA solutions to be implemented	-Innovative monitoring strategies -Hydrogeological and reactive-transport models	-Innovative monitoring strategies and sensors monitoring -Hydrogeological and reactive-transport models	Treatment technologies	Treatment technologies

-Treatment
technologies

Table 3: Summary of case studies, CS1 to CS4

3 NINFA solutions and specifications of their application in case studies

Initial specifications of the sensors and technologies which will be developed and optimized first in lab scale and then implemented at pilot scale will be described in section 3. Detailed specifications will be provided in D1.2 at the end of the NINFA project.

3.1 Sensors

3.1.1 Initial state-of-the-art (SOTA) on sensors

Currently, GW flow is not directly analysed, but estimated by measuring pressure in piezometers, an approach which is limited by the heterogeneity of the subsurface. Recent research has showed the potential of fibre optics-based sensors in providing continuous high-resolution real-time information about the aquifer temperature and flow. However, to make these sensors even more relevant for GW quality protection, their capabilities need to be extended, specifically regarding pollutants found in drinking water wells. Moreover, in order to allow risk-based actions, the measurement of the toxic potency rather than the mere presence of pollutants is required.

3.1.1.1 Fibre optics-based sensors

Fibre optic cables can be installed vertically into the subsurface with a direct push technique¹⁹ and provide continuous high-resolutions real-time information about the aquifer. From the investigation of a previous project, different type of fibre optics-based sensors for groundwater flow monitoring were studied²⁰, including Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS) and one based on Fibre Bragg Gratings (FBGs). DTS allows for the measurement of temperature along the length of the fibre optical cable, and when combined with a heating cable, DTS also allows for the measurement of flow velocities. This was demonstrated at a well field of a drinking water company (Vitens). Recent research at Wetsus showed the potential of FBG based fibre optics sensors²¹.

FBGs are basically individual sensors developed by inscribing refractive index modulations onto the core of a fibre optical cable which is capable of reflecting a particular wavelength²². This reflection is affected by bending, stretching or compression of the cable. FBG is an established technique in the aerospace industry²³, environmental and biochemical applications, structure health monitoring²⁴, and many other fields but was until recently not used for groundwater sensing. FBGs can sense anything that creates an alteration in the factors determining the reflected Bragg wavelength from temperature, strain, refractive index, pressure, vibration, humidity and many more (Figure 16)²⁵.

Figure 16. Basic principle of Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBG)

FBGs are compact, easy to fabricate and have exceptional multiplexing capabilities. They are also capable of withstanding harsh environments, which make the technology suitable for sensing in complicated aquifer systems. However, the capabilities of FBG sensors for geohydrological and water quality measurements can be further expanded. Therefore, novel approaches are needed to develop distributed chemical sensing. Preferably, approaches that can be integrated with distributed sensing of hydrogeological parameters. At the first stage, Wetsus aims to increase the capability of the fibre-optic sensor to trace the transport of salt or pollutants towards drinking water wells in coastal aquifers as seen in (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Remote sensing unit of FBG sensors installed for monitoring saltwater intrusion in the coastal aquifers in order to identify composition of drinking water

3.1.1.2 Bioassay sensor for detection and quantification of the genotoxic potency of hydrophilic pollutants

Current chemical methods have limitations in efficiently measuring various contaminants found in water sources. The detection of hydrophilic compounds poses challenges in terms of extraction, and the identification of unknown compounds such as metabolites and reaction products are also difficult²⁶. Furthermore, these chemical methods do not provide information about the potential toxic effects of these compounds and their mixtures. In contrast, bioanalytical tools, also known as bioassays, can determine the toxic potency of bioactive pollutants present in water samples. However, most existing bioassays are either highly specific to a few compounds or offer only non-specific indications of general toxic effects. Therefore, there is a pressing need for an efficient and cost-effective test that can evaluate the toxic potency of compound mixtures in water samples.

3.1.2 Specifications of application of novel sensors in CS2

The NINFA project (WP2) aims to develop a cost-effective monitoring strategy that combines existing sensors and analytical approaches with novel tools (GenTox for detecting and quantifying the genotoxic potency of hydrophilic pollutants, and distributed sensors based on fibre optics for measuring GW flow and changes in chemical composition), which will be validated in CS2 (Los Alcazares, Murcia, Spain) in Summer 2025.

In NINFA, the GW flow monitoring with fibre optics-based sensors will be expanded with capability to measure salinity and changes in the chemical composition (overall quality) of the GW through Refractive Index sensing. Moreover, the high-resolution real-time temperature sensing capability will enable the tracing of infiltrating surface water due to the slight temperature differences. Together this will allow on-site high-resolution real-time monitoring of water quality and flow without the need of piezometers or tracer-injection.

Groundwater quality is influenced by various factors and contaminants. A multi-sensor device allows for the simultaneous measurement of multiple parameters, providing a more comprehensive understanding of groundwater quality²⁷. In NINFA, a multi-sensor device will be developed which will combine the novel fibre optic sensor for salinity measurements and several commercial sensors in order to monitor several physico-chemical parameters (pH, temperature, flow, redox, conductivity, salinity, nitrates). The list and measurement ranges of the proposed commercial sensors can be found in Table 4.

Probe	Unit	Range	Comment
pH		1 to 12	<u>CPS11E</u>
Temp.	°C	-15 to 80	From pH or redox sensors
Redox	mV	-1500 to 1500	<u>CPS12E</u>
Conductivity	µs/cm	1 to 500000	<u>CLS82E</u>
Nitrate	mg/L	0.1-50	<u>Viomax CAS51D</u>

Table 4: List and measurement ranges of commercial sensors

The electrodes will be placed in a flow cell, which will collect the sample and allow measurements to be conducted. A data logger connected to the system will be used to collect and manage data. A physical model will be built at the Wetsus lab in order to calibrate and test the device's capabilities. The specifications of the sensors (such as sensitivity, accuracy, and repeatability) will be determined. The sensors' compatibility with the device's design will be investigated. To ensure that the device is suitable for field deployment and can withstand environmental conditions, the architecture and physical layout which consider the overall size, power requirements, and connectivity options (e.g., wired or wireless) will be evaluated. Finally, the device's integration with the data acquisition system will be tested to ensure that the system can deliver accurate results with high temporal resolution. The data acquisition system will also be used to collect data from the fibre optics sensor, which will be installed along the well's screen. The fibre optic sensor for salinity measurement is still under development at Wetsus lab.

Concerning the bioassay sensor, Wetsus and Wageningen University developed an invertebrate bioassay (Hy-GenTox) using a nematode species (*Caenorhabditis elegans*) that can simultaneously identify and quantify the toxic potency of multiple compounds in a water sample, without requiring extraction²⁸. This bioassay was based on analyzing the genetic response of the nematode, which can provide insights into the specific toxic mechanisms involved and help determine the nature of the toxicants present. Additionally, the magnitude of the genetic response could be indicative of the concentration of exposure to these toxic compounds. The Hy-GenTox chip will be optimized for the automated detection of toxic pollutants.

Advanced samplings campaigns in different sampling points in Los Alcázares will be undertaken. This intensive monitoring and high-frequency acquisition obtained from the multi-sensor device and the

novel fibre optic-based sensor will help improve the reliability and accuracy of GW simulation modelling. Increased data availability will aid in determining the impact of regulatory strategies on diffuse pollution spreading (rather than just current interventions), as well as stressors (drought/flooding).

3.2 Technologies for preventing groundwater contamination and overexploitation

3.2.1 Initial SOTA on technologies for preventing groundwater contamination and overexploitation

In Europe, only approximately 16% of treated wastewater is currently being reused²⁹, and reclaimed water lacks comprehensive characterization regarding potential pollutants that could pose risks to health and the environment. These pollutants include CECs, MPs, and contaminants like ARBs and ARGs. Furthermore, the predominant application of reclaimed water is for agricultural irrigation, which necessitates water transportation and thus incurs high economic and environmental costs. On the other hand, environmental uses such as aquifer recharge are still in the early stages of implementation (as observed in projects like MARSOL, MARSoluT, and SPONGE).

Among possible technologies for in-situ water reuse, NBS are promising solutions which provide multiple ecosystem services (greening the environments, promoting biodiversity, air pollution control, abatement of heat island effect, ...), so their implementation in cities is being promoted (MULTISOURCE, UrbanGreenUP, NICE projects). However, their use in urban water management is usually limited to reduce flood risk, rather than treating runoff water for its reuse or safe indirect aquifer recharge. NBS removal capacity of priority pollutants (including HCs and MP) is low or unknown, while technologies for heavy metals removal/recovery, studied at lab scale, focus mainly on acid dissolution of metallic ions (mainly copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), zinc (Zn) and lead (Pb))^{30,31}. Membrane based technologies could be an interesting approach for the removal and recovery of metals³² and potentially for the recovery of high valued metals like Pt and Pd.

AOPs are well known for their capacity to remove CECs, MPs, pathogens, and industrial pollutants^{33,34}. Despite the limited available data, AOPs also show great potential in addressing the escalating issue of ARGs and ARBs³⁵. The presence of ARBs and ARGs could be attributed to the inadequate removal of pharmaceuticals such as antibiotics by municipal WWTPs and the contamination of agricultural runoff with antibiotics excreted by animals. However, AOPs can be costly due to the requirements of chemical reagents and electricity. Promising cost-cutting approaches which include the use of less costly reactors like race way ponds and combination of AOPs with other technologies (e.g. NBS, biofiltration, membranes)^{36,37} need to be evaluated.

In a rural context, the complex composition and quantity of manure requires an on-site treatment solution to avoid contamination of soils and GW with nutrients, heavy metals (mainly Cu and Zn), pathogens and antibiotics (RESOURCE, FERTIMANURE projects), while locally recovering fertilisers and water for irrigation. Moreover, an important part of the applied pesticides and fertilisers end up in GW (especially when using recycled manure), for which retention measures must be applied. In all cases,

there is a need of cost-effective in-situ technologies to prevent GW contamination and allow resource recovery. Diverse technologies have been developed to remove contaminants and pathogens from manure³⁸ ensuring its safe use as fertilizer. Concurrently, nutrient retention measures such as the use of biochar have been studied, reporting variable efficiencies (28-50%)³⁹, which could be optimized for enhanced performance.

NINFA will provide sustainable solutions for avoiding GW pollution and boosting safe water reuse at local scale (treatment of WWTP effluent and cities runoff and manure treatment). 4 different trains of technologies that can be easily introduced within both urban and rural scenarios will be developed and investigated. These technologies will be optimised under technoeconomic criteria, ensuring the absence of HCs, CEC, and MP, evaluating the fate of ARGs, and recovering high added value materials.

3.2.2 Specifications of application of treatment technologies in Case study 2 (Los Alcázares, Murcia, Spain)

Within WP3, NINFA will undertake the development of a series of technologies aimed at reducing the leaching of nutrients, pesticides, and various pollutants (such as metals and antibiotics) from manure into GW. This will be achieved by enhancing the quality of the resulting products, such as safe organic fertilizers and inoculated HTC-biochar. Additionally, the application conditions of these products in crops will be optimized at pot/field scales.

The manure treatment process will begin with solid/liquid separation. The liquid fraction will undergo several treatment steps, including microfiltration for nutrient concentration and removal of particulate solids, stripping with membrane contactors to obtain ammonium salt solution, and AOP employing solar photo-Fenton in a raceway pond configuration for disinfection, removal of antibiotics, and potential inactivation of ARGs. This process will result in the production of a safe liquid fertilizer.

The solid fraction of the manure will be transformed into high-performance biochar using HTC technique. To enhance plant nutrient uptake and minimize nutrient leaching, the obtained biochar will be inoculated with plant growth-promoting bacteria. This approach will reduce the required dose of fertilizers. The resulting high-performance biochar, along with the fertilizers obtained from the liquid fraction, will be subjected to pot tests to determine the optimal dosage for plant growth and evaluate their impact on soil quality parameters such as pH, salinity, texture, organic matter content, and microbial biodiversity. These tests will also assess the reduction in nutrient/pesticide leaching compared to existing methods, particularly the use of manure, which is a common practice that contributes to soil and groundwater contamination. The technologies developed will be validated using real manure and soil samples obtained from CS2.

Finally, the implementation of a wood chip bioreactor and a bio electrowetland will be evaluated in parallel for the removal of nitrates from the upper layers of groundwater. To decrease environmental and economic impacts, local recycled materials from the agricultural area will be evaluated.

3.2.3 Specifications of application of treatment technologies in Case study 3 (Terrassa, Barcelona, Spain)

NINFA (WP3) will propose two trains of technologies for urban runoff treatment:

- Modular-prefabricated NBS combined with innovative AOP system will be implemented for HC and MP removal. The NBS system will be developed incorporating low-cost/recycled adsorbent materials and testing different plant species and configuration designs, keeping subsurface water flow to avoid the appearance of mosquitoes (vector-borne diseases). Their combination with AOP will be evaluated for the maximization of hydrocarbons removal and water disinfection. The treated water will be considered for indirect aquifer recharge or other uses such as street cleaning, irrigation, etc., thus reducing aquifer exploitation depending on the quality. Solar photo-Fenton will be evaluated as AOP using a compound parabolic collector (CPC) reactor, able to concentrate up to 10 suns through its geometric reflective shape in the case where the NBS effluent is reused. The reaction will be carried out at neutral pH, considering the use of organic chelating agents (e.g., ethylenediamine-N,N'-disuccinic acid or nitrilotriacetic acid) to increase iron (Fe) solubility and avoid its precipitation. In case that the NBS effluent will serve for indirect aquifer recharge, UV-assisted titanium dioxide (TiO₂) photocatalysis will be evaluated for the removal of hydrocarbons, while soil infiltration will be evaluated to determine the capacity of soil to further remove suspended particulate matter, MP, nutrients, and heavy metals.
- A combination of membrane concentration, chemical extraction and centrifugal and/or electromagnetic separation will be employed for the recovery of heavy metals with a focus on selectively extracting neglected platinum group elements (PGEs) in addition to Cu, Ni, and Zn. A membrane-based technology (electrodialysis) will be evaluated and optimized for concentrating the high added value metals present in road runoff. By means of chemical dissolution with membrane separation, the metals in ionic form will be removed while insoluble platinum group elements will be retained. Ionic species may be recovered and concentrated by electrodialysis, a technology that applies a voltage difference between two ion selective membranes increasing the concentration of the initial ions present in the feed. Non-ionic species will be in metallic form and thus can be concentrated by pressure driven membrane separation processes based on their size. This concentrated effluent will be treated by centrifugation for the recovery of big particles or electromagnetic technologies for non-decantable ones, obtaining metals in solid form.

These technology trains will be optimized at lab scale and validated at pilot scale with real runoff water from a selected site in Terrassa.

3.2.4 Specifications of application of treatment technologies in Case study 4 (WWTP Butry-sur-Oise, Ile-de-France, France)

NINFA, under WP3, proposes a combination of *low cost* AOP, AC (adsorption and/or bioadsorption) and BF for the removal of CECs and MPs as well as evaluating the fate of ARGs present in WWTPs.

Photo-Fenton treatment will be implemented and optimized as AOP, considering the use of raceway ponds instead of CPC to decrease costs. The utilization of AOP unit process serves as a means to oxidize non-biodegradable CECs originating from the secondary treatment of WWTPs. In fact, AOP can lead to the formation of simpler compounds that could be easily adsorbed on AC and potentially further better biodegraded. Additionally, the AOP unit serves as a disinfection operation, allowing for the evaluation of the removal or inactivation of ARGs. Refractory pollutants will be removed by adsorption on AC. The efficiency of using a combination of various AC types will be assessed, including AC derived from urban biomass, aiming to enhance circularity in the treatment process while simultaneously reducing costs and environmental impact. The activated carbon fixed bed could be used separately or coupled with a BF process which will combine the adsorption phenomenon and the regeneration of the activated carbon through microbial degradation. Finally, a filtration step (slow sand filtration) will be evaluated to assess its capacity to remove the rest of the pollutants (e.g., MP).

Technologies will be optimized (individually and in combination) at lab scale and further validated at pilot scale at the WWTP in CS4 (Butry-sur-Oise).

4 Overview of European and national legislation relevant to the implementation of NINFA solutions

NINFA seeks to treat wastewater for their reuse for several purposes depending on the quality (fit-for-purpose use) and generate high value-added materials with the aim of preventing GW pollution and over-exploitation.

It is important to ensure that the solutions proposed do not contravene existing European and national regulations. Some of the main current relevant European and national regulations that will impact NINFA Solutions are summarized in Table 5. Their impact and those of any other relevant existing and/or future legislations on implementation NINFA solutions will be investigated and discussed in detail as part of task 1.4 and presented in deliverable D1.2.

REGULATION			AIM	LEVEL
Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC			Establishes a framework for the protection of all waters including groundwater and focuses on ensuring good qualitative and quantitative status of waterbodies.	European
Ground Water Directive 2006/118/EC			Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution.	European

Regulation (EU) 2020/741	Lays down minimum water quality requirements for the safe reuse of treated urban wastewaters for agricultural irrigation between EU countries.	European
Regulation (EC) 1063/2009	Lays down health rules regarding these animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption.	European
Regulation (EU) 2019/1009	Provides a framework which now allows bio-based fertilisers and tailor-made fertilising products on the EU market and introduces limits for toxic contaminants.	European
Nitrate Directive 91/676/EEC	Aims to protect water quality from pollution caused by agricultural sources and to promote the use of good farming practices.	European
Royal Decree 1620/2007	Establishes a legal framework for the reuse of treated wastewater for 5 intended reuse categories and lays down minimum water quality requirements.	National (Spain)
Ministerial Order of June 25, 2014 amending the order of August 2, 2010	Establishes a legal framework for the reuse of treated wastewater for the irrigation of agricultural crops or green spaces and specifies minimum water quality requirements.	National (France)

Table 5 : Selected European and national regulations relevant to NINFA

5 Conclusion

In this deliverable, the four EU case studies where NINFA solutions will be implemented were described in order to highlight the concern regarding groundwater status. The solutions that the NINFA project seeks to develop and implement including the innovative sensors and treatment technologies were also described. Finally, the KPIs and validation strategy to measure the efficiency of the proposed solutions were also briefly described.

6 References

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